

Microhodotermes viator
nov. subspecies
Southern Harvester Termite

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

© D. Gergonne

Group: Insect

Size: 0.5 - 1 cm in length

Distribution:

The southern harvester termite (*Microhodotermes viator*) is found throughout Southern Africa.

Importance:

Microhodotermes viator is widely distributed across Southern Africa and plays an important role in soil composition. Namaqualand populations are associated with some of the oldest active termite mounds in the world, highlighting the species' ecological significance.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 29.43 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 9.45 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 0.93 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 97.3% [Single: 95.0%, Duplicated: 2.3%]

BUSCO database: insecta

Assembly N50: 8 207.35 kilobases

Contig number: 1183

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